

consortium

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FOOD CoST

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Redefining the value of food.

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What is FOODCoST?

FOODCoST is a European funded project that aims to support the transition towards sustainable food systems by (i) proposing a harmonising methodology to calculate true costs of food (ii) formulating strategies to internalize externalities in business models and policy and (iii) assessing the impact of those strategies on sustainability.

Why? Did you know that current food systems are not sustainable?

They generate substantial environmental, social and health costs while failing to provide affordable food for healthy diets to all.

One of the central problems is that these costs are **externalised**, which means they are not reflected in the market prices and, therefore, are also not reflected in the decision-making of actors in food value chains.

That's why we are...

- **Internalising these externalities** based on less distorted cost and price information which is fundamental to facilitating market-based responses and contributing to more sustainable production and healthier consumption patterns;
- Harmonizing the methodology to calculate true costs;
- Assessing the impact of the strategies to internalize externalities.

Our Action Plan

01

Build a Stakeholder Platform supporting the transition towards a sustainable food system.

02

Create a harmonised methodology for the Valuation of Externalities and an EU-global database of externality data.

03

Develop a framework for the Internalisation of Externalities through policies and business models and strategies.

04

Assess the Impact of internalising externalities and outline the **FOODCoST** Roadmap.

Methodology How?

By implementing a methodology where the stakeholder platform serves as the base for 3 main pillars:

Valuation

Development of a harmonised methodology to calculate external costs and benefits and database development.

Internalisation

Internalisation of externalities through policy interventions and business models and strategies and development of tools.

Impact

Scenarios' definition and impact assessment.

